

Conversations on communities, digital content and the professional historian

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In this blog, Dr Stefan Ramsden from the OHOS History Lab at the University of Manchester reflects on the project's interactions with academic historians and their involvement with community-generated digital content.

As part of the History Lab's work we've spoken with a wide range of academic historians at seminars and conferences about the OHOS project and community-generated digital content; we have also had feedback on draft papers from reviewers and peers. As our project reaches its final stages, we use this blog to reflect on what these conversations reveal about how professional historians view digital historical source material collected and shared by communities.

The first point is that social and cultural historians have been highly sympathetic to our argument that community-produced histories can reshape academic perspectives and give space to previously marginalised voices. It has surprised us how many of the historians we have talked to about the project have experience of producing historical outputs with community history groups. Digital history experience is also relatively widespread, with many professional historians participating in digital projects which, while not always community focussed, are similarly concerned with how to make digital material available and linkable. Many have pointed out that the problems of finding, linking and preserving digital historical materials is common to both academic-led and community-led projects.

However, despite considerable interest in and sympathy for our project and for the principle of community engagement, we have not often encountered historians who routinely use CGDC as source material in the same way that they use professionally managed collections in institutional and state archives. There are three main reasons for this: professional identification with a particular model of 'archival research'; lack of knowledge about CGDC; fears of using material where provenance, intellectual property rights and expectations around ethical engagement are not always clearly defined.

While academic historians may not routinely use CGDC for their own research, some find it a useful resource for teaching. Pedagogically, local history topics can be used for engaging students and for framing discrete and manageable dissertation topics; there are many CGDC collections which provide university teachers with valuable and easily accessible source material for local history subjects. Academics who use CGDC for teaching note that this class of material is particularly fruitful for encouraging students to reflect critically on source materials: because CGDC often has less complete metadata and provenance information than material found in standard archival collections, it may require additional procedures for determining validity and reliability.

At OHOS we have explored ethical and intellectual property rights issues that surround the use of CGDC (see the OHOS blog 'A free resource for all?'). We contend that, because CGDC often refers to living people, because the processes behind its collection are not always precisely described, and because the groups who collect and disseminate this material feel a strong sense of ownership towards it, historians need to tread carefully in using CGDC and pay close attention to the wishes and historical interpretations of the community groups with which it is associated. We suggest that using CGDC may involve a commitment to an element of coproduction, in which historians' uses and interpretations of the material includes negotiation with the wishes and interpretations of the groups who collected it. Professional historians are in general sympathetic to these ethical considerations. Oral historians in particular are well attuned to ethical issues around authority and interpretation. Indeed, some historians have wanted us to go further in exploring how the historical profession might offer something to the groups who produce CGDC. Others have suggested that the use of any historical source material involves ethical decisions (for example, about representation of the dead, and around our right to tell stories about particular groups we are not ourselves part of) and therefore that our special ethical pleading for CGDC is misplaced. Some professional historians have pointed out that coproduction is not always appropriate: the historian's training and vocation require her to exercise critical independence in her interpretation of CGDC as evidence which can shed light on wider historical questions.

In presenting our case-studies to seminars and conference audiences, some historians noted that we have focussed on examples that illuminate the history of minority and under-represented groups in British society, but have not presented stories from the kinds of groups who are probably responsible for the majority of CGDC – white middle-class and working-class local historians interested in the history of their town, village, industry etc. We accept that this material also has importance for shedding light on everyday life in the past, and we will showcase some of this CGDC in future publications.

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